

ON THE FORMATION OF LEGAL CULTURE IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL PERSON FROM THE VIEWPOINTS OF GREAT THINKERS

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Annotation The reforms carried out to further increase the legal culture of our population, young people, especially entrepreneurs, through the development of various directions of entrepreneurial activity in our republic, the views of our great thinkers on entrepreneurship presented in classic written sources are discussed.

Key words: public welfare, youth, entrepreneur, legal culture, reforms, legal-normative foundations, socio-economic and legal nature, society, law, justice, politics.

Adoption of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" and "2024 - the year of supporting youth and business" [1] for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to increase the welfare of the people to a new level [1] - can be seen as a logical continuation of systematic reforms to further increase the legal culture of our population, young people, especially entrepreneurs.

The socio-economic and legal essence of the strategic reforms implemented to develop the legal culture of entrepreneurial activity, legal and normative bases that regulate it, professional special culture of an entrepreneur lies. Judging by historical sources, the roots of entrepreneurial activities go back to the distant past. We know that until the 16th century, the main tributary of the "Great Silk Road" passed through our country, and we can see that trade, trade, and handicrafts developed widely. In this sense, in some national-mental views, the view that entrepreneurship was originally settled in the form of trade has been dominant.

In classical written sources, in particular, in "Avesta", the philosophical and moral thoughts praising human work, condemning laziness, ideas teaching hard work, the well-being of society and human life are specially recognized [2]. Also, in the sacred sources of Islam, special attention is paid to entrepreneurship and its religious and legal issues [3].

Philosophical doctrines developed in ancient Greece focused on the issue of entrepreneurship. For example, Plato in his work "Laws" "paying attention to the issue of the relationship between the state and business, it is possible to strengthen the relationship between them only in the conditions of economic

freedom" [4], according to the great philosopher Aristotle, "An entrepreneur should engage in fair work, regularly engage in good work." The opinions of [5] emphasize the socialization of entrepreneurship.

The great Eastern thinker Abu Nasr Farabi in his work entitled "The City of Virtuous People" makes a special mention of open-handed entrepreneurs. According to Farabi, "A community that brings happiness to a person is a truly virtuous, mature, characteristic community. The feeling of caring about a person's future, his happiness, sharing his sorrows should be formed in entrepreneurs" [6]. Abu Nasr Farabi pays special attention to the place of laws in the development of entrepreneurship in society. That's why the Allama said, "The leader should issue laws about trade that will not harm anyone, even about the measurement of weight, grain, and sugar-like things. At the same time, it is necessary for the legislator to reflect the situation of all rich and poor people in the laws, so that the category of people who break the laws and renew the vices without correcting their people to the end is not overlooked" [7]. By Abu Rayhan Beruni, opinions such as "...the main factor of mutual voluntary agreement of people in their views on trade (entrepreneurship)" [8] are put forward.

Ibn Sina's opinion that "... trade (entrepreneurship) should be managed by the help of just laws adopted on the basis of mutual agreement of people" [9] explains the importance of legal culture. The statesman and politician Amir Temur in his "Tuzuklar Temur" states that business relations should be regulated based on the criteria of justice. Also, his words "...I looked at everyone equally seriously and fairly, I did not differentiate anyone from another" [10] are a reflection of the democracy of that time. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, also mentioned the following views of the entrepreneur Amir Temur on the issue of entrepreneurship: "Personally, every time I read "Temur's tricks", I feel as if I have found some kind of spiritual strength. In my career, I have repeatedly referred to this book, and I have been convinced many times how vital the wise thoughts in it, which never get old, are food for human spirituality even today. For example, it is clear to all of us that the words "I have seen in my experience, one determined, enterprising, alert, brave and ambitious person is better than a thousand inactive and indifferent people" [11].

Entrepreneurship was mainly formed in the 18th century, and it is often explained in connection with the concept of "proprietor". It is worth noting that the concept of entrepreneurship was given a special definition for the first time by R. Cantillon, a well-known English economist who lived in this period. Later,

I. Kant, F. V. Hegel, J. J. Rousseau, and S. L. Montesque showed a special initiative regarding the development of entrepreneurship and its social, legal and philosophical foundations. The following liberal-democratic views of the great French politician, sociologist and philosopher Charles Louis Montesque can be cited: "Freedom is not the right to do what a person wants, but the right to perform only the actions reflected in the laws, explaining that human activities can be carried out only through laws " highlights [12]. These liberal views serve as an important theoretical-conceptual basis for the development of entrepreneurial activity and the improvement of the legal culture of an entrepreneur even in our time.

John Locke, considered one of the leaders of the idea of "liberalism" in the West, emphasizes that the duty of the state is to protect its entrepreneurs from foreign competitors, to ensure the inviolability of private property, and to maintain order. V. Petty also defends free enterprise in his socio-philosophical views. He considered private property "Sacred" and "Inviolable" [13].

Currently, the issue of entrepreneurship is interpreted on the basis of various socio-philosophical concepts even within the CIS countries. In particular, V.S. Avtonomov explained entrepreneurship based on an anthropological approach and said that "in entrepreneurship, a person's rational decisions and creativity in functional management come in handy" [14], while the author of the term "limited opportunity" related to entrepreneurship, G. Simon said, "In entrepreneurship, a certain balance and states that an optimal environment is necessary" [15].

Rational and existential aspects of increasing the legal culture of an entrepreneur were studied by V. G. Makeeva, Yu. A. Pompeev, A. D. Kuzmichev, I. N. Shapkin, M. A. Romyantsev. For example, V. G. Makeeva writes that "An entrepreneur should be smart, enlightened, cultured, have the highest moral qualities, always live in the spirit of work, creativity, creativity" [16]. With this, the author notes ethics as the only criterion in the formation of entrepreneurial culture. But in the formation of the entrepreneur's culture, first of all, along with moral principles (conscience, honesty, purity), legal literacy is required. In Yu.A.Pompeev's works, "Many of the formed ideas about the characteristics of an entrepreneur have been severely criticized as bourgeois and capitalist ideology under the influence of various reasons, especially during the authoritarian regime. As a result of this, economic backwardness occurred in the society. "Today, it is necessary to eliminate such backwardness and restore new areas of entrepreneurship." However, although the author noted his suggestions in this

regard, he did not take into account the legal criterion that develops entrepreneurship. A.D. Kuzmichev, and I.N. Shapkin, "The experience of history shows that entrepreneurs have the ability to widely use available opportunities to solve their problems. Of course, free enterprise has gone through a long process of development. That is why this industry has a strong economic and legal basis.

In our country, the work of modern entrepreneurs, who promoted modern forms of business activity, was of great importance in bringing the country out of feudal backwardness. Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulla Avloni, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdulla Qadiri, Abdulhamid Cholpon and others can be included in the list of such progressive and enlightened moderns. "After all, the social, cultural and economic ideas of the Jadids in their time to renew and modernize the people's life and improve their economic situation in the society had an impact not only in their time, but also later on the development of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan." It should be noted that in order to increase the legal culture of the entire society, young people, especially entrepreneurs, it is related to the composition of all the elements of the legal culture that are part of their general culture.

At the new stage of our country's development, entrepreneurship and its various ways of development are detailed in the works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, and special attention is paid to this issue in the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan". In this "Strategy of Development", the theoretical foundations, strategic goals, priorities, problems and ways of solving them are explained in detail in the transition to a digital and green economy and the development of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. It can be seen that President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev was active in developing conceptual approaches to various aspects of entrepreneurship. For example, in the work "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan", it is necessary to know the essence of professional knowledge and laws, which is characteristic of the character and nature of the Uzbek people, and for leaders and entrepreneurs to show high results as a result of their activities, as well as maintaining the organic connection between our national values and legal norms. It is necessary to take into account the spiritual aspect, and based on other aspects, it is shown what measures should be implemented in various sectors of our economy.

References:

1. <https://uzlidep.uz/news-of-party/11446>
2. Avesta. Translation by A. Makhkamov. - Tashkent: Sharq, 2001. - B. 248.

3. Rakhmanov A.R. Human rights and individual status in Islamic jurisprudence. Ph.D. ... diss. - Tashkent: 2002. Khaidarov H.F. A factor of knowledge and management of the processes of societal laws-reforms. fake f.d. ... diss. - Tashkent: 2002. Eshonjanov B.I. The position of Imam al-Bukhari in the cultural life of Mavorunnahr of the 9th century and jurisprudential issues in his work "Al-Jami al-sahih". Ph.D. ... diss. - Tashkent: 2000. Komilov M.M. The role of Alauddin al-Samarkandi in the development of the science of jurisprudence in Mavorunnahr and the importance of the work "tuhfat al-fuqaho". Ph.D. ... diss. - Tashkent:2000. Бахадиров Р.М. Из истории классификации наук на средневековом мусульманском Востоке. - Ташкент: Академия, 2000. - Б. 244.
4. Plato. Laws. (Translated from Russian by Orfon Otajon.) - Tashkent: New Age Generation, 2002. - В. 95-96.
5. Aristotle. Politics. Hair. V.4-x tomax. - Т.4. - Moscow: Mysl, 1984, - S. 379.
6. Farabi Abu Nasr. City of virtuous people. - Tashkent: "Khalq Merosi" publishing house named after A. Qadiri, 1993. - В. 186.
7. Farabi Abu Nasr. City of virtuous people. - Tashkent: "Khalq Merosi" publishing house named after A. Qadiri, 1993. - В. 38.т. - Москва: 2001; Тутов Л.А. Философия хозяйства. Опыт духовного преображения. - Москва: 2003.
8. Abu Rayhan Beruni. Selected works, Volume I, 1968. - В. 268.
9. Ibn Sina. Laws of medicine: a selection of 3 volumes/Editors: U. Karimov, H. Khikmatullaev. - Tashkent: "People's heritage named after A. Qadiri" publishing house, - J I. 1992. - В. 142.
10. Amir Temur. Timur's rules. - Tashkent: G'. Ghulom publishing house, 1996. - В. 53-55.
11. Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an irresistible force. - Tashkent: Spirituality, 2008. - В. 176.
12. Монтескье Ш. О духе законов. - Москва: 1955. - С. 163.
13. Антология экономической классики. (В двух томах) Т.1. - Москва: Эконов. 1991.
14. Автономов В.С. Модель человека в экономической науке. - С-Петербург: 1998. - С. 12.
15. Саймон Г. Рациональность как процесс и продукт мышления//THESIS. 1993. - С. 74.
16. Макеева В.Г. Культура предпринимательства. - Москва: 2002. - С. 124.